

MILD STEEL CORROSION INHIBITION IN SULPHURIC ACID SOLUTION USING SOME SCHIFF BASE COMPOUNDS

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Abstract

In this study, Schiff Bases compounds were prepared and used as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in sulphuric acid solution. Tafel polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements techniques were used to examine the effect of these compounds. Schiff Bases inhibition effect depends on their concentrations, presence of different function groups and the temperature of the electrolyte. Thermodynamic adsorption parameters (K_{ads} and ΔG_{ads}°) of the studied inhibitors were calculated using the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The inhibition efficiency enhanced by the presence of synergism ion in the solution.

1. Introduction

One of the best methods of protecting metals against corrosion involves the use of inhibitors, which are the substances that slow down the rate of corrosion. The majority of well-known inhibitors are organic compounds containing heteroatoms, such as O, N or S, and multiple bonds. These compounds allow an adsorption on the metal surface [1,2]. the condensation product of an amine and a ketone or aldehyde with general formula of $R_2C=NR$ is well-known as Schiff bases inhibitors [3]. Agrawal, *et al*, revealed that the inhibition efficiency of Schiff bases is much greater than that of corresponding amines and aldehydes due to the presence of a $-CH=N-$ group in the molecules [4]. The polar unit is regarded as the reaction center for the adsorption process. Thus, polar organic compounds are adsorbed on the metal surface, forming a charge transfer complex bond between their polar atoms and the metal. The adsorption of these molecules depends mainly on certain physicochemical properties such as functional groups, steric factor, aromaticity, electrondensity at the donor atoms and p-orbital character of donating electrons [5-7]. In the present work, some Schiff bases were synthesized and evaluated for their inhibition towards mild steel corrosion reaction in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution. In addition to test the experimental data with several adsorption isotherms at different temperatures, in order to determine the standard free energy of the adsorption process from one side and gain more information on the mode of adsorption of the inhibitor on the electrode surface from other side.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis of inhibitors

All Schiff bases (Inhibitors) were synthesized by the condensation of equimolar mixture of N-Aminophthalimide (A) and different aldehydes in ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed then cooled over night to obtain the compounds. The obtained product was filtered, washed, and dried by filtration under vacuum. Equation 1 shows the reaction between N-Aminophthalimide and different aldehydes. The different groups of aldehydes, the IUPAC name of inhibitors and reaction time are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. The IUPAC name of the inhibitors.

X	Reaction time	Product name	Symbol
p-OCH ₃	3.5 h.	2-(4-methoxybenzylideneamino)isoindoline-1,3-dione	B
2,4,6-OCH ₃	3 h.	2-(3,4,5-trimethoxybenzylideneamino)isoindoline-1,3-dione	C

2.2. Sample preparation

The mild steel sheets were abraded with a series of emery paper (grade 320–500–800–1000–1200). After that, they were washed with bidistilled water and acetone and dried in alcohol. They were embedded in epoxy resin, to expose a geometrical surface area of 1 cm² to the electrolyte. The chemical composition of tested carbon steel alloy is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Chemical composition of mild steel alloy.

Fe	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Al	Mo	Ti	Co
Rent	0.23	0.13	0.58	0.035	0.03	0.06	0.024	0.06	Nil	Nil	Nil

2.3. Electrochemical measurements

The Electrochemical measurements were carried out at 25°C using a Voltalab 40 Potentiostat (PGZ 301, Radiometer Analytical, France). A platinum wire was used as auxiliary electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) served as reference electrode. A piece of mild steel (1 cm²) was used as working electrode. Before Electrochemical experiments, the electrode was allowed to corrode freely and its open

circuit potential (OCP) was recorded as a function of time up to 30 min. After this time, a steady-state OCP, corresponding to the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) of the working electrode, was obtained. The polarization study was carried out at a scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} . The potential range used in the experiment was between -700 mV and -200 mV Vs. SCE. The IE (%) was calculated by Equation 2 [8].

$$\text{IE (\%)} = 1 - \frac{i_{\text{Corr(inh)}}}{i_{\text{Corr(uninh)}}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where $i_{\text{Corr(uninh)}}$ and $i_{\text{Corr(inh)}}$ are the corrosion current densities for steel electrode in the uninhibited and inhibited solutions, respectively. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were carried out in a frequency range of 100 kHz to 50 mHz with amplitude of 10 mV peak-to-peak using ac signals at open circuit potential. The inhibition efficiency IE (%) was calculated from Equation 3 [8] :

$$\text{IE (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{R_{\text{ct}}^0}{R_{\text{ct}}}\right) \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where R_{ct}^0 and R_{ct} are the charge transfer resistances in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution without and with different concentrations of the synthesized inhibitors, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of inhibitors concentration

Polarization measurements were carried out in order to get information concerning the kinetics of the anodic and the cathodic reactions. Potentiodynamic polarization curves for inhibitors (A, B and C) in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 at 25 °C for specimens in the presence of various concentrations of inhibitor and inhibitor with 1 mM of KI are shown in Figures (1, 2 and 3). Electrochemical parameters such as corrosion potential (E_{corr}), corrosion current density (i_{corr}), cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes (b_c and b_a) and inhibition efficiency were calculated and listed in Tables (2, 3 and 4). From the obtained polarization curves, it is clear that the corrosion current densities (i_{corr}) decreased with increasing concentration of each inhibitor. Inhibitor A has the lowest efficiency because it has the lowest electron density. Adding a phenyl group increases the electron density but methoxy group decreases it in benzene ring so the inhibition efficiency of inhibitor B is greater than inhibitors C. Moreover, as the number of methoxy groups increase, the nonplanarity of compound increases [9]. Therefore, inhibitor B is more planer than inhibitor C. Thus, inhibitor B makes bonds with surface of steel easier than inhibitor C.

Addition of iodide ions to Inhibitor- H_2SO_4 systems results in marked decrease in the corrosion current density (i_{corr}) as shown in Figures (1b, 2b and 3b). As shown in Table 4, when 1 mM KI was added into the 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution containing 1 mM of inhibitor B, the current density reduced from $346 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$ to $253 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$. Accordingly, the percentage of inhibition efficiency increased up to 82.7% also.

The presence of anodic breakdown potential (Figures (1b, 2b and 3b)) reflects the formation of anodic protective films on the electrode surface due to adsorption of iodide ions. There are two mechanism of inhibitor's performance enhancement by iodide ions: (1) The iodide ions are first adsorbed on the metal surface and the

inhibitor is then drawn to the double layer by the adsorbed halide ion, (2) The iodine ions form ion-pair with inhibitors in the bulk solution before being adsorbed on the metal surface [10]. The synergistic inhibition brought about by the combination of inhibitor and iodide ions can be explained on the basis that halide ions have a greater tendency to be adsorbed on the surface in attraction with organic cations. Generally if the shift of E_{corr} is >85 mV with respect to E_{corr} of uninhibited solution, the inhibitor can be viewed as either cathodic or anodic type [11]. In the present study the maximum shift of E_{corr} is 74 mV, suggesting that tested inhibitors act as a mixed type inhibitors for mild steel specimens in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 .

Figure 1. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of steel electrode immersed in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution without and with different concentrations of inhibitor A in (a) absence and (b) presence of 1mM of KI.

Figure 2. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of steel electrode immersed in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution without and with different concentrations of inhibitor B in (a) absence and (b) presence of 1mM of KI.

Figure 3. Potentiodynamic polarization curves of steel electrode immersed in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution without and with different concentrations of inhibitor C in (a) absence and (b) presence of 1mM of KI.

Table 3 Tafel parameters and IE (%) in absence and presence of KI for inhibitor A.

Inhibitor A (M)	KI (M)	$-b_c$ (V/dec)	b_a (V/dec)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	$-V_{corr}$ (V)	IE%
Blank	-----	0.112	0.097	1465	0.465	-----
Blank	1×10^{-3}	0.116	0.252	1260	0.465	13.9932
1×10^{-5}	-----	0.115	0.156	1349	0.461	7.91809
1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.109	0.252	913	0.477	37.6792
5×10^{-5}	-----	0.093	0.114	1193	0.461	18.5666
5×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.081	0.177	848	0.494	42.116
1×10^{-4}	-----	0.134	0.098	1085	0.443	25.9386
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.097	0.23	706	0.494	51.8089
2.5×10^{-4}	-----	0.154	0.104	976	0.439	33.3788
2.5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.09	0.166	674	0.507	53.9932
5×10^{-4}	-----	0.148	0.111	871	0.439	40.5461
5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.093	0.118	619	0.515	57.7474
1×10^{-3}	-----	0.161	0.088	723	0.429	50.6485
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	0.098	0.163	541	0.539	63.0717

Table 4 Tafel parameters and IE (%) in absence and presence of KI for inhibitor B.

Inhibitor B (M)	KI (M)	-b _c (V/dec)	b _a (V/dec)	I _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	-V _{corr} (V)	IE%
Blank	-----	0.112	0.097	1465	0.465	-----
Blank	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.116	0.252	1260	0.465	13.9932
1 x 10 ⁻⁵	-----	0.106	0.102	921	0.457	37.1331
1 x 10 ⁻⁵	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.094	0.175	732	0.469	50.0341
5 x 10 ⁻⁵	-----	0.073	0.086	762	0.464	47.9863
5 x 10 ⁻⁵	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.104	0.214	609	0.46	58.43
1 x 10 ⁻⁴	-----	0.086	0.092	629	0.456	57.0648
1 x 10 ⁻⁴	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.1	0.217	451	0.467	69.215
2.5 x 10 ⁻⁴	-----	0.11	0.086	512	0.436	65.0512
2.5 x 10 ⁻⁴	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.087	0.183	379	0.471	74.1297
5 x 10 ⁻⁴	-----	0.097	0.08	395	0.443	73.0375
5 x 10 ⁻⁴	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.096	0.147	292	0.487	80.0683
1 x 10 ⁻³	-----	0.137	0.087	346	0.429	76.3823
1 x 10 ⁻³	1 x 10 ⁻³	0.103	0.112	253	0.49	82.7304

Table 5 Tafel parameters and IE (%) in absence and presence of KI for inhibitor C.

Inhibitor C (M)	KI (M)	$-b_c$ (V/dec)	b_a (V/dec)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	$-V_{corr}$ (V)	IE%
Blank	-----	0.112	0.097	1465	0.465	-----
Blank	1×10^{-3}	0.116	0.252	1260	0.465	13.9932
1×10^{-5}	-----	0.086	0.094	972	0.459	33.6519
1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.101	0.299	809	0.477	44.7782
5×10^{-5}	-----	0.089	0.121	861	0.458	41.2287
5×10^{-5}	1×10^{-3}	0.096	0.207	723	0.465	50.6485
1×10^{-4}	-----	0.079	0.089	685	0.456	53.2423
1×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.132	0.185	567	0.452	61.2969
2.5×10^{-4}	-----	0.096	0.097	569	0.463	61.1604
2.5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.141	0.133	518	0.454	64.6416
5×10^{-4}	-----	0.065	0.101	482	0.461	67.099
5×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	0.094	0.116	421	0.465	71.2628
1×10^{-3}	-----	0.048	0.073	376	0.471	74.3345
1×10^{-3}	1×10^{-3}	0.099	0.084	305	0.473	79.1809

The synergistic inhibition effect was evaluated using a parameter S_{Θ} obtained from the surface coverage values (Θ) of the anions, cations and both. The surface coverage (θ) was calculated by Equation 4 [12].

$$\Theta = \frac{i_{\text{Corr}}(\text{uninh}) - i_{\text{Corr}}(\text{inh})}{i_{\text{Corr}}(\text{uninh})} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Aramaki and Hackerman [13] calculated the synergism parameter S_{Θ} by Equation 5

$$S_{\theta} = \frac{1 - \theta_{1+2}}{1 - \theta'_{1+2}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where $\Theta_{1+2} = (\Theta_1 + \Theta_2) - (\Theta_1 \Theta_2)$, Θ_1 is the surface coverage by anion, Θ_2 is the surface coverage by cations and Θ_{1+2} is the measured surface coverage by both the anions and cations. At $S_{\theta} > 1$, a synergistic effect is obtained because of a co-operative adsorption. In case of $S_{\theta} < 1$, antagonistic behavior prevails due to a competitive adsorption. The synergism parameter S_{Θ} were calculated and listed at Table 6.

Table 6. The synergism parameter, S_{θ} , for each inhibitor.

Inhibitor concentration (M)	Synergism parameter (S_{Θ})		
	A	B	C
1×10^{-5}	1.27	1.08	1.03
5×10^{-5}	1.21	1.08	1.03
1×10^{-4}	1.32	1.2	1.04
2.5×10^{-4}	1.24	1.16	0.95
5×10^{-4}	1.21	1.16	0.99
1×10^{-3}	1.15	1.18	1.19

The S_{θ} values were found to be higher than unity (Table 6), suggesting the synergistic action of iodide ion with these inhibitors and it can be concluded that the iron surface is positively charged. these results may be explained as following; iodide ions are able to improve adsorption of the organic cations by forming the intermediate bridges between the positively charged metal surface and the positive end of the inhibitor [10]. Adding a benzene ring to N-Aminophthalimide to obtain Schiff bases leads to decrease the positive charge on Schiff bases because the benzene ring is electron-rich, therefore the electrostatic interaction between Schiff bases and iodide ions decreases.

3.2. EIS measurements

Impedance spectroscopy is one of the most powerful non-destructive methods of investigating the boundaries between materials with different types of conductivities [14]. EIS is based on the analysis of interactions between an object and alternating current (ac) probing signals of different frequencies. The

ac response of electrochemical systems is highly frequency dependent and contains valuable information about different processes which take place simultaneously at the electrode/electrolyte interface. Classical EIS data analysis consists of two stages: (i) elucidation of an appropriate physical model of the system and (ii) fitting of EIS data to the model to estimate the parameters of the models [15]. In this study, the corrosion behavior of mild steel in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution in the absence and presence of 1 mM of each inhibitor was studied by EIS. In general, the impedance spectra exhibited one single depressed semicircle, and the diameter of the semicircle increases with the increase of inhibitor efficiency. The semicircle can be attributed to the charge transfer that takes place at electrode/solution interface, and the transfer process controls the corrosion reaction of mild steel. Nyquist and Bode plots of mild steel in uninhibited and inhibited solutions containing 1 mM of each inhibitor are shown in Figures. 4a and 4b, respectively. The equivalent circuit model used for fitting the impedance spectra is shown in Figure 4a.

Figure 4. (a) Nyquist plots and the equivalent circuit model (inset) used for fitting the impedance spectra and (b) Bode plots of mild steel in uninhibited and inhibited 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solutions containing 1 mM of each inhibitor.

The constant phase element, CPE, is introduced in the circuit instead of a pure double layer capacitor to fit more accurately the behavior of the electrical double layer. The values of R_{ct} were given by subtracting the high frequency impedance from the low frequency one from Equation 6 [16]:

$$R_{ct} = Z_{re} \text{ (at low frequency)} - Z_{re} \text{ (at high frequency)} \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

The correction in the capacitance to its real value (C_{dl}) is calculated at the frequency f_{max} by Equation 7 [17]:

$$C_{dl} = P (\omega_{max})^{n-1} \quad \text{Eq.7}$$

Table 7 Results of EIS data fitting by equivalent circuit.

	R_s	R_{CPE}	R_L	P	n	L (H)	R_{ct}	IE (%)	C_{dl}
	($\Omega.cm^2$)	($\Omega.cm^2$)	($\Omega.cm^2$)	($\mu F.cm^{-2}$)			($\Omega.cm^2$)		($\mu F.cm^{-2}$)
Blank	1.4449	8.66371	1.62	4.75E-05	0.93751	0.050984	7.21881	-----	28.32
A	1.5007	14.673	1.8458	9.58E-05	0.8138	0.21099	13.1723	45.19704	21.39
B	1.4166	32.218	7.0254	6.02E-05	0.85156	0.102	30.8014	76.56337	18.86
C	1.8084	28.003	4.8327	7.75E-05	0.81413	0.098598	26.1946	72.44161	20.68

Where P is the magnitude of the CPE, $\omega_{max} = 2\pi f_{max}$; f_{max} is the frequency at which the imaginary component of the impedance is maximal and n is a factor that satisfies the condition $0 \leq n \leq 1$, which indicates how far (0), or how close (1), the interface is from being treated as an ideal capacitor. The parameters n and C_{dl} are independent of frequency. R_s represents the ohmic resistance between the working and the reference electrode; R_{CPE} is the charge transfer resistance related to the corrosion reaction at OCP; CPE is the capacitance of the electric double-layer at the electrode/electrolyte interface; L is the inductor related to the relaxation process obtained by adsorption species and R_L is the resistance of the inductor. The values of R_s , R_{CPE} , R_L , P , n , L , R_{ct} and C_{dl} were listed in Table 7. The examination of the results of Table 7 enables to deduce that the R_{ct} values and IE (%) increased when inhibitors were added to the system, indicating that inhibitor molecules adsorb on the metal surface and form a protective film on the metal-solution interface [18]. These results together with those obtained from the Tafel polarization experiments at the same concentration confirm the inhibition efficiencies of the tested inhibitors decreases in the order: $B > C > A > \text{Blank}$. C_{dl} values decreased when inhibitors were added. It may be caused by a reduction in local dielectric constant and/or by an increase in the thickness of the electrical double layer. These observations suggest that inhibitor functions by adsorption on the metal surface, thereby causing a decrease in the C_{dl} values and an increase in the R_{CPE} values with decreasing of n value, when compared to that obtained in pure 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution. This can be attributed to a certain decrease of the initial surface heterogeneity resulting from the inhibitor's adsorption on the most active centers [19]. The presence of inductive R_L - L loop at the lower frequency range may be attributed to the relaxation process obtained by adsorption species like SO_4^- and H_{ads}^+ on the electrode surface. It may be also attributed to the re-dissolution of the passivated surface at low frequencies [20].

3.3. Effect of temperature

The temperature can modify the interaction between the steel electrode and the acidic medium in the absence and presence of the inhibitors. In order to study the effect of temperature on the inhibition efficiencies of the Schiff bases, polarization experiments were conducted in the range of 298–348 kelvin, in the absence and presence of 1 mM of inhibitor. Values of associated electrochemical parameters and IE (%) for all the inhibitors studied are given in Table 8. The corrosion current density increased with

increasing temperature both in uninhibited and inhibited solutions. In order to calculate activation parameters for the corrosion process, Arrhenius Equation (Eq.8) and transition state Equation (Eq. 9) were used [21]:

$$r = \lambda \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$r = \frac{RT}{Nh} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H^*}{RT}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where r is the corrosion rate which related to corrosion current density (i_{corr}), λ is the Arrhenius pre-exponential factor, T is the absolute temperature, E_a is the activation corrosion energy for the corrosion process. h is the Planck's constant, N is the Avogadro's number, ΔS^* is the entropy of activation, ΔH^* is the enthalpy of activation. (E_a), ΔS^* and ΔH^* at 1 mM of inhibitors are calculated by linear regression between $\ln(i_{\text{corr}})$ and $1/T$ (as shown in Figure 5) and the result is listed in Table 8. All the linear regression coefficients are close to 1, indicating that the steel corrosion in H_2SO_4 solution can be elucidated using the kinetic model.

Table 8. The relation between IE% of each inhibitor and Temperature

Temperature (k)	IE (%)		
	A	B	C
298	50.65	76.38	74.34
308	48.28	68.51	61.54
318	44.14	61.61	56.22
328	42.22	56.61	52.54
338	38.63	53.29	50.21
348	36.38	50.99	45.33

Figure 5. Arrhenius plots of $\ln(i_{\text{corr}})$ versus $1/T$ for mild steel in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution

Figure 6. Plots of $\ln(i_{\text{corr}}/T)$ versus $1/T$ for mild steel in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution.

Table 9. E_a , ΔH^* and ΔS^* of the dissolution of carbon steel in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 in the absence and presence of 1 mM of investigated inhibitors.

Inhibitor	E_a (KJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^* (KJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J/k mol ⁻¹)
Blank	26.86959	24.20031	-142.192
A	31.4321	28.76282	-132.79
B	39.30465	36.63537	-111.712
C	37.09602	34.42674	-117.472

From Figure 6 Straight lines are observed with a slope of $(\Delta H^*/R)$ and an intercept of $(\ln(R/Nh) + \Delta S^*/R)$ from which the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* are calculated and also listed in Table 9. The positive signs of the ΔH^* reflect the endothermic nature of the steel dissolution process and that mean the dissolution of steel is difficult. The negative values for ΔS^* in the inhibited and uninhibited systems imply that the activation complex in the rate determining step represents association rather than dissociation step, which means that a decrease in disorder takes place on going from reactant to the activated complex [21]. The E_a values for inhibited systems are higher than E_a for uninhibited systems (Table 9). Therefore, physical adsorption occurs in the first stage that explains the nature of organic molecules –metal interactions and also mean that the inhibitor is adsorbed on the most active adsorption sites (having the lowest energy) and the corrosion process takes place predominantly on the active sites of higher energy [22].

3.4. The adsorption isotherm

When inhibitor is added to acid solution, it blocks the active sites of the metal surface by adsorption process to decrease corrosion rate. The plot of C/θ versus C gave a straight line as shown in Figure 6. The linear regression coefficients (R^2) are almost equal to 1, confirming that the adsorption of studied inhibitors in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 solution follows the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. The Langmuir isotherm [23], Equation 10, was found to fit well with the experimental data obtained for the five investigated compounds.

$$\frac{C}{\theta} = \frac{1}{K_{ads}} + C \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where C is the inhibitor concentration in the bulk of solution, θ is the surface coverage ($\theta = (IE\%)/100$) and K is the adsorption–desorption equilibrium constant which is related to the standard free energy adsorption, ΔG_{ads}^0 at a single temperature can be calculated from Equation 11:

$$\Delta G_{ads}^0 = -RT \ln (55.5 K) \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

where 55.5 is the molar concentration of water, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the temperature in Kelvin. The values of linear regression coefficients (R^2), K_{ads} and ΔG_{ads}^0 were listed in Table 8.

Table 8. The values of linear regression coefficients (R^2), K_{ads} and ΔG_{ads}^0 .

Inhibitors	R^2	$K_{ads} (M^{-1})$	$\Delta G_{ads}^0 (KJ/mol.)$
A	0.986	4.95	-13.890047
B	0.998	25	-17.89568923
C	0.997	18.52	-17.15360839

Figure 7. The relation between (C/θ) versus C .

$\Delta G_{\text{ads}}^{\circ}$ of the inhibitors on mild steel showed negative values indicating the spontaneity of the process. The value of $\Delta G_{\text{ads}}^{\circ}$ up to -20 kJ/mol. is an indication of the electrostatic interaction of the charged molecule and the charged surface of the metal (physisorption) while $\Delta G_{\text{ads}}^{\circ}$ is more negative than -40 kJ/mol. implies that inhibitor molecules are adsorbed strongly on the metal surface through coordinate type bond (chemisorption) [24]. The range of calculated $\Delta G_{\text{ads}}^{\circ}$ values for rest inhibitors are ranging between -14 kJ/mol and -19 kJ/mol. This indicated that adsorption of these inhibitors on the mild steel surface is physical adsorption [25]. The possible adsorption mechanism is electrostatic interaction between the charged inhibitor molecules and charged mild steel surface. In the other words, the direct adsorption is because of donor-acceptor interactions between the lone pairs of electrons of hetero-atoms, p-electrons of benzene and heterocyclic rings and the vacant d-orbitals of iron surface atoms.

Conclusion

The Schiff bases have been synthesized and tested as corrosion inhibitors. All of them have inhibition efficiency for mild steel in 0.5 M H_2SO_4 and The excellent inhibition efficiency was attributed to the adsorption of inhibitor molecules and protective film formation on the metal surface. Polarization measurements showed that the prepared inhibitors are mixed-type inhibitors, inhibiting the corrosion of mild steel by blocking the active sites of the metal surface. Addition iodine ions to system increases inhibition efficiency. Generally, Double-layer capacitances of these inhibitors decrease with respect to the blank solution. It may be explained based on adsorption of these inhibitors on the mild steel surface. The adsorption of Schiff bases molecules on the metal surface from solution obeys Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The standard free energy of adsorption has been found less than -20 KJ/mol, which indicated that the adsorption between the Schiff bases and the surface is physical bond.

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